

Empowering Rural and Tribal Women in Tamil Nadu: A Regression Analysis of Banking Schemes and Socio-Economic Development

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the impact of banking schemes and financial inclusion on the socio-economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil Nadu. Despite various government initiatives to expand financial access, many women remain excluded due to poor accessibility, low financial literacy, and socio-cultural barriers. The study focuses on three major dimensions of financial inclusion: access, availability, and usage of banking services. Primary data were collected from 384 respondents across selected districts using a structured questionnaire. Statistical techniques such as factor analysis and multiple regression were applied to examine relationships between variables. The findings identify key determinants of financial inclusion, including service accessibility, loan availability, information dissemination, and usage patterns. Factor analysis grouped these into components like approachability, loan support, promotion, and service utilization. Regression results show a strong and statistically significant relationship between financial inclusion and socio-economic development indicators such as growth, employability, stability, social upliftment, and standard of living. Education emerged as a key factor influencing financial participation, while other socio-economic variables had a comparatively lower impact. The study concludes that improving financial literacy, strengthening banking infrastructure, and promoting awareness of financial schemes are essential to enhance inclusion and empower rural and tribal women for sustainable development.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion, Banking Schemes, Rural Women, Tribal Women, Socio-Economic Development, Financial Literacy, Empowerment, Inclusive Growth

INTRODUCTION

Across the world, developing economies are seeking effective mechanisms to eradicate poverty and ensure the participation of every citizen in economic growth and socio-economic development. In India, the government has a long-standing commitment to expanding financial access to marginalized and underprivileged populations, particularly in rural areas, with the objective of fostering inclusive and sustainable development. Providing banking facilities and financial services to financially excluded communities is essential for building a strong and resilient economy. Several barriers, such as the lack of identity proof, inadequate infrastructure, and the geographical distance between banks and residential areas, continue to contribute significantly to financial exclusion. Over the years, the Government of India has implemented various initiatives to address these

challenges. The nationalization of major private sector banks in 1969 marked a critical phase in reducing economic exclusion. Subsequently, the expansion of rural bank branches led to public sector banks accounting for nearly 56 percent of total rural branches by 2022. Furthermore, microfinance initiatives through the formation of Self-Help Groups (SHGs) have played a vital role in empowering economically disadvantaged communities. The implementation of the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) significantly enhanced financial inclusion by promoting bank account ownership. Since its inception, more than 46.25 crore beneficiaries have been brought into the formal banking system, with deposits totaling ₹1,73,954 crores. In addition, the Reserve Bank of India introduced the Kisan Credit Card scheme, benefiting nearly 76 million farmers by providing them with

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timely access to institutional credit. The Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations (ICRIER) has also developed a Financial Inclusion Index to assess the reach of banking services, in which India ranked 38th in the availability and usage dimensions. Despite the positive outcomes of these initiatives, a substantial portion of the population remains outside the formal financial system. Recognizing this gap, the Reserve Bank of India continues to emphasize universal financial inclusion as a key driver of inclusive growth. Although India has achieved impressive economic growth over the past two decades, persistent inequalities continue to undermine social cohesion and may constrain long-term development (Zhuang & Hasan, 2008). Sustainable growth must therefore be inclusive and broad-based, encompassing all sectors and segments of society (George, 2011). Inclusive finance and socio-economic development contribute significantly to economic growth, improvement in living standards, poverty reduction, income equality, agricultural development, and employment generation (Deutscher & Jacquet, 2009). Consequently, financial inclusion has emerged as a central theme in the global development agenda. It serves as a foundation for inclusive growth and sustainable development (Sadakkadulla, 2007; Subbarao, 2010). Financial inclusion is commonly defined as ensuring access to affordable, timely, and adequate financial services, particularly for vulnerable and disadvantaged groups. In recent years, developing countries have increasingly prioritized financial inclusion and socio-economic development as key policy objectives. Numerous initiatives have been undertaken to enhance public awareness and participation in formal financial systems. Ultimately, inclusive growth and sustainable socio-economic development can be achieved by extending financial services and promoting financial literacy among financially excluded populations, especially in rural areas.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Asian Development Bank (2000), in its report *“Finance for the Poor: Microfinance Development Strategy,”* emphasized that in the absence of an inclusive formal financial system, poor individuals and small entrepreneurs are compelled to rely on informal sources of finance. Although such sources

provide timely and easy access, they impose high interest burdens. The study highlighted that financial inclusion helps reduce poverty and inequality by enabling access to credit, savings, and insurance facilities, which support investment and consumption smoothing. Crafts (2002), in *“The Human Development Index 1870-1999: Some Revised Estimates,”* analyzed long-term trends in human development. The study concluded that the Human Development Index presents an optimistic view of twentieth-century economic development, particularly emphasising improvements in life expectancy as a major achievement contributing to human welfare. Littlefield et al. (2003), in their study *“Is Microfinance an Effective Strategy to Reach the Millennium Development Goals?”* examined the impact of microfinance on development outcomes. The findings revealed that access to financial services positively influences nutrition, health, education, and women’s status within households, thereby contributing to poverty alleviation. Treasury (2004), in the report *“Promoting Financial Inclusion,”* analyzed both demand-side and supply-side factors responsible for financial exclusion. Demand-side factors were described as self-exclusion, while supply-side factors included inadequate banking services and lack of financial guidance. The report also outlined various government initiatives aimed at reducing exclusion. Leeladhar (2005), in *“Taking Banking Services to the Common Man – Financial Inclusion,”* emphasized the need for banks to adopt innovative strategies to expand their outreach. The study recommended collaboration with microfinance institutions and local communities and highlighted the importance of no-frills accounts and technological innovations in extending banking services to remote areas. Mohan (2006), in his article *“Economic Growth, Financial Deepening, and Financial Inclusion,”* examined the relationship between financial exclusion and economic growth. The study stressed the importance of financial deepening and advocated the provision of affordable, secure, and accessible financial products such as savings accounts, credit, insurance, and remittance facilities to strengthen inclusion and enhance credit delivery. Agarwal (2007), in *“100 Percent Financial Inclusion: A Challenging Task Ahead,”* analyzed the status of financial inclusion in India. The study found significant variations among states in bank account

ownership. It also observed that while deposit shares declined in rural and semi-urban areas, metropolitan regions witnessed continuous growth. The unequal distribution of credit indicated banks' preference for high-potential regions, leading to the exclusion of poorer sections. Kumar, Singh, and Kumar (2007), in their study *"Trends in Rural Finance: Performance of Rural Credit and Factors Affecting the Choice of Credit Sources,"* highlighted regional and household disparities in credit flow. The study revealed that less educated and poor households were largely excluded from institutional credit. It recommended simplifying loan procedures to improve access for marginalized groups. Chelliah and Shanmugam (2001), in *"Some Aspects of Inter-District Disparities in Tamil Nadu,"* analyzed income and development disparities among districts in Tamil Nadu. The study revealed significant inequalities in income and human development. Income inequality was found to be higher than disparities in human development, with low agricultural productivity and social backwardness identified as major causes. Kauhal (2007), in *"Performance of Women's Self-Help Groups in District Moradabad, Uttar Pradesh,"* examined the relationship between socio-economic characteristics and group processes among SHG members. Based on a sample of 160 respondents, the study found that group processes were positively related to education, participation, trust, and cohesiveness. Participation in SHGs enhanced women's self-confidence, empowerment, and capacity-building abilities.

Statement of the Problem

India has made significant progress in promoting financial inclusion through various government policies, regulatory reforms, and institutional initiatives. Programs such as the expansion of rural banking networks, promotion of self-help groups, and implementation of financial inclusion schemes have contributed substantially to improving access to formal financial services. Despite these efforts, a considerable proportion of the adult population, particularly in rural and tribal areas, continues to remain outside the formal banking system. The vast size of the population, regional disparities, and pronounced differences between urban and rural regions have posed major challenges to achieving universal financial inclusion. Limited physical access to banking institutions, inadequate infrastructure, low

levels of financial literacy, lack of proper identification documents, and socio-cultural constraints further restrict the participation of marginalized communities in formal financial systems. In addition, the high cost of service delivery and the difficulty of establishing sustainable, efficient banking mechanisms in remote, geographically isolated areas have exacerbated the problem. As a result, many low-income households continue to depend on informal sources of finance, which often involve higher risks and exploitative interest rates. Access to affordable, reliable, and timely financial services is widely recognized as a crucial component of socio-economic development. Financial inclusion enables individuals to save securely, access credit for productive activities, manage financial risks, and invest in education, health, and livelihood opportunities. Consequently, greater emphasis has been placed on extending financial services to economically weaker sections of society. Inclusive finance serves as an effective instrument in addressing the multidimensional nature of poverty by enhancing income-generating capacities, promoting social empowerment, and improving overall living standards (Nalini & Mariappan, 2012). However, existing financial inclusion initiatives have not been equally effective across all regions and social groups, particularly among rural and tribal women, who often face additional barriers related to education, mobility, and decision-making power. There is a need for systematic empirical investigation to assess the actual impact of banking schemes and financial inclusion programs on their socio-economic development. Understanding the extent to which these initiatives have improved financial access, economic participation, and quality of life is essential for designing more inclusive, efficient, and sustainable policies. This study, therefore, seeks to examine the effectiveness of banking schemes in promoting socio-economic development among rural and tribal women in Tamil Nadu.

Objective and Methodology of the Study

Empowering Rural and Tribal Women in Tamil Nadu: A Regression Analysis of Banking Schemes and Socio-Economic Development. The research is mainly based on rural and tribal areas and will be collected from sample respondents through a survey, using the questionnaire developed for the purpose. A

well-structured interview schedule questionnaire was designed and distributed to 384 respondents from selected areas to gather the required data for this research. Before data collection, a pilot study was undertaken, and 80 questionnaires were distributed to respondents from rural and tribal districts in Tamil Nadu. Based on the responses obtained, certain modifications were made to that questionnaire, and the final instrument was developed and distributed, and the data from the sample respondents were collated. The percentage analysis is used for studying

the demographic profile. The study comprises rural and tribal women from rural and tribal districts in Tamil Nadu. The rural and tribal districts are Nilgiris, Krishnagiri, Dharmapuri, Ariyalur, Viluppuram, Vellore, Cuddalore, and Tiruvallur. The multistage random sampling method was used to determine the sample size using the Krejcie and Morgan Table. The Limitations are confined only to the eight rural districts; hence, the results cannot be generalized to the other remote and hill areas.

Table 1: List of banking variables used for factor analysis of exogenous variables of inclusive finance

Access	
X1	The bank location is near your place
X2	ATM service is available near your place
X3	ATM is easy to use
X4	Bank is easily approachable
X5	Banking services are accessible to old age people
X6	Bank employees promptly redress your problems
X7	In an emergency, the approach of the Bank is easy
X8	Useful information can be accessed easily
X9	Bank employees provide sufficient bank information
X10	The overall access to banking services satisfied you
X11	The bank manager responds to your queries
X12	Sufficient bank employees are needed to meet customer requirements
X13	The bank employees are easily accessible when you needed
Availability	
X14	The loan is available easily
X15	Good saving schemes are available for rural peoples
X16	Self-help group loans are available
X17	The Bank provides insurance services
X18	The Bank provides a debit card facility
X19	Locker facility is Available
X20	The loan is available within the time limit
X21	A new passbook is issued when customers ask
X22	The procedure for getting a loan available is easy
X23	Help desk/ assisting people help to fill the deposit/withdrawal challans
X24	Banking infrastructure is there as per customer requirements
X25	You are satisfied with the banking services available to you
X26	Banks are collecting hidden charges
X27	New interest rate information provided by banks on time
X28	Updating new banking schemes are available to customers
X29	Fieldworkers talk about different banking schemes that are helpful to rural people.
X30	Employees are explaining about new schemes available to rural peoples
Usage	
X31	Saving money frequently
X33	Withdraw money frequently
X33	Using the credit facilities of the Bank
X34	Insurance premiums paid through banks
X35	Loan payments are made through the Bank
X36	Depositing money at the Bank frequently
X37	Using new banking schemes
X38	Regularly vising the bank branches

X39	Interest on credit is low compared to outside lenders
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Reliability Statistics and Explanatory Factor Analysis for Exogenous Variables.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis of variables of factor analysis		
Cronbach's Alpha Vale	Cronbach's alpha value based on standardized items	No. of Items
0.864	0.793	39

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 shows Cronbach's alpha coefficient for reliability analysis of the inclusive finance variables. The reliability analysis, which reflected the exogenous variables building the elements of financial inclusion, yielded 0.864 for 39 items after excluding any item with a value less than 0.50.

Additionally, the items affecting the factors and consistency of the scale were eliminated through item-wise analysis using metrics such as "scale mean if the item deleted; scale variance if the item deleted; squared multiple correlations; corrected item-total correlation; and the corrected alpha value if the item deleted."

Table 3: Result of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

KMO measure of sampling adequacy		0.834
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	(Approx. Chi-Squire)	3.017E3
	Df	173
	Sig.	0.000*

Source: Primary Data*Indicates a 5percent level of significance

Table 3 reveals the significant link between the variables: Bartlett's Test of Sphericity and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measures of sample adequacy (KMO). The data's statistical significance is assessed using Bartlett's test of sphericity. The test statistic's value

and the corresponding significance level below 0.05 demonstrate that the variables have a strong association. A KMO rating of sampling adequacy of 0.834 indicates that factor analysis might be regarded as a suitable method for data analysis. Furthermore, the chi-square value is substantial ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the data is suitable for factor analysis.

Table 4: Factor analysis results for exogenous variables

Variables	Components							Communalities
	Accessing of Banking Services and Schemes							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
X1	0.789							0.673
X2	0.756							0.642
X3			0.675					0.613
X4			0.598					0.469
X5	0.704							0.592
X6	0.746							0.632
X7	0.631							0.599
X8		0.721						0.611
X9		0.699						0.512
X10		0.543						0.436
X11	0.573							0.471
X12		0.598						0.483

X13	0.569							0.476
Availability of Banking Services and Schemes								
X14				0.798				0.693
X15				0.756				0.643
X16				0.763				0.676
X17				0.673				0.576
X18				0.654				0.534
X19				0.645				0.541
X20				0.598				0.586
X21				0.571				0.534
X22				0.567				0.541
X23				0.711				0.654
X24				0.708				0.646
X25					0.524			0.416
X26				0.643				0.511
X27				0.696				0.591
X28				0.694				0.586
X29					0.677			0.567
X30					0.689			0.574
Usage of Banking Services								
X31							0.608	0.542
X32							0.632	0.572
X33						0.598		0.493
X34							0.763	0.671
X35						0.511		0.436
X36						0.533		0.432
X37							0.786	0.674
X38						0.674		0.524
X39						0.622		0.549

Table 4 shows the factor analysis done based on three dimensions like: accessing banking services and schemes, Availability of banking services and schemes, and Usage of banking services; The analysis of the principle component and rotate loading are

based on 39 variables and converted them into 7 factors, those factors are “Approachability of Services”, “Acceptability of Information”, “ATM services”, “Loan services support and assistance”, “Promotion”, “Specific usage”, and “General usage”.

Table 5: List of banking variables used for factor analysis of endogenous variables of inclusive finance

Social Status	
X1	Banks made you independent in decision-making
X2	Bank has improved your financial education
X3	Banks have changed your personality and lifestyle
X4	Banks increase your level of confidence
X5	Banks have improved your technical skills
X6	Family helping you to in your business ideas
X7	Banks helped your social empowerment (purchase of cow, tv, etc)
X8	Banks helped you to overcome financial crises and social development
X9	Banks helped household development
X10	You discuss with the people and social groups regarding banks' products and services (financial inclusion things)
X11	Like to change your lifestyle
X12	Participating in community activities
X13	In society, you can make decisions independently, which will help you bring changes.
X14	Banks have empowered you to move public places freely

X15	Free to move any self-help-groups any other kind of support
X16	Socially independent and more developed after being covered under the banking inclusion.
Economic Status	
X17	Banks have reduced your need to borrow money
X18	Banks increase your standard of living
X19	You are assisted while deciding where the savings are to be used
X20	Banks has made independent regarding the spending of your savings
X21	Banks directly affect capital formation and investment in agriculture
X22	Banks enhance your source of income
X23	Banks enabled you and your family to enjoy better economic status
X24	Banks increased access to financial inclusion in society
X25	Ban has led to the progress of your neighbors
X26	Banks developed the production of goods and services in your area
X27	Banks increase your economic activities
X28	Banks have reduced the financial stress in your life
X29	Banks increased productivity in the agricultural sector

Reliability Statistics and Explanatory Factor Analysis Endogenous variables

Reliability Analysis

The reliability analysis provides an overall indication of the scale's internal consistency or repeatability as well as the degree to which the items in the

questionnaire are connected. The most used metric for assessing the overall scale's dependability is Cronbach's alpha. Cronbach's alpha has a universally accepted lower bound of 0.70. For 29 variables, Cronbach's alpha in the examination of beneficiaries' attitudes regarding banking services is 0.834. This is more in line with 0.70, which is deemed acceptable under the reliability analysis rule of thumb.

Table 6: Reliability analysis for Endogenous variables

Cronbach's Alpha Value	Cronbach's alpha value based on standardized items	No. of Items
0.834	0.763	29

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 shows Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The reliability analysis, which reflected the exogenous variables building the elements of financial inclusion, yielded 0.834 for 29 items after excluding any item with a value less than 0.50. Additionally, the items

affecting the factors and consistency of the scale were eliminated through item-wise analysis using metrics such as "scale mean if the item deleted; scale variance if the item deleted; squared multiple correlations; corrected item-total correlation; and the corrected alpha value if the item deleted."

Table 7: Result of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

KMO measure of sampling adequacy	0.849
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Approx. Chi-Squire)	2.016E3
Df	244
Sig.	0.000*

Source: Primary Data

* Indicates 5percent level of significance

Table 7 reveals that the data are suitable for factor analysis by displaying the two tests. Bartlett's Test of

Sphericity and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measures of sample adequacy (KMO). The data's statistical significance is assessed using Bartlett's test of sphericity. The test statistic's value and the corresponding significance level below 0.05 which

demonstrate that the variables have a strong association. A KMO rating of sampling adequacy of 0.849 indicates that factor analysis might be regarded as a suitable method for data analysis. Furthermore, the chi-square value is substantial ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the data is suitable for factor analysis.

Table 8: Factor analysis of endogenous variables

Variables	Components						Communalities
	Accessing of banking services and schemes						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
X1		0.746					0.623
X2		0.714					0.612
X3		0.707					0.607
X4		0.581					0.498
X5			0.788				0.659
X6		0.689					0.623
X7		0.678					0.619
X8			0.776				0.631
X9			0.684				0.692
X10			0.643				0.596
X11	0.728						0.671
X12	0.718						0.653
X13			0.571				0.487
X14	0.709						0.603
X15	0.699						0.591
X16	0.691						0.573
X17				0.712			0.616
X18				0.702			0.592
X19				0.699			0.632
X20						0.645	0.589
X21						0.754	0.621
X22				0.577			0.498
X23						0.606	0.536
X24				0.578			0.487
X25				0.667			0.583
X26					0.598		0.506
X27					0.556		0.486
X28						0.578	0.493
X29					0.651		0.572

Table 8 shows the factor analysis done based on two dimensions: social status and economic status. In these two dimensions, we analyzed and finalized 29 variables and converted them into six factors: liberation, social upliftment, the standard of living, stability, employability, and growth.

Multiple Regression Analysis

H01: There is no significant difference in access of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu.

Table 9: Access of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.997 ^a	.995	.985	1.65880	.995	98.29	6	3	.002*

<p>Source: Computed Data *Indicates Statistical Significance at 5 Per cent Level a. Dependent variable: Availability b. Predictors (Constant), Growth, Standard of Living, Stability, Liberation, Employability, Social Upliftment</p>

The above table 9 reveals the regression analyses of access of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu. The independent variables are Growth, Standard of Living, Stability, Liberation, Employability, Social Upliftment which are statistically significant at 5 per cent level, and the adjusted R square value of these variables has demonstrated that more than 98 per cent influence the

dependent variables. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference between access of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu.

H01: There is no significant difference in availability of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu.

Table 10: Availability of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.986 ^a	.973	.919	1.928	.973	17.96	6	3	.019*
<p>Source: Computed Data *Indicates Statistical Significance at 5 Per cent Level c. Dependent variable: Availability d. Predictors (Constant), Growth, Standard of Living, Stability, Liberation, Employability, Social Upliftment</p>									

The above table 10 depicts the regression analyses of availability of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu. The independent variables are Growth, Standard of Living, Stability, Liberation, Employability, Social Upliftment which are statistically significant at 5 per cent level, and the adjusted R square value of these variables has demonstrated that more than 91 per cent influence the

dependent variables. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference between availability of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu.

H01: There is no significant difference in usage of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu.

Table 11: Usage of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	1.000 ^a	1.000	.999	.182	1.000	2102.24	6	3	.000*
<p>Source: Computed Data *Indicates Statistical Significance at 5 Per cent Level a. Dependent variable: Usage</p>									

b. Predictors (Constant), Growth, Standard of Living, Stability, Liberation, Employability, Social Upliftment

The above table 11 demonstrates the regression analyses of usage of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu. The independent variables are Growth, Standard of Living, Stability, Liberation, Employability, Social Upliftment which are statistically significant at 5 per cent level, and the adjusted R square value of these variables has demonstrated that more than 99 per cent influence the dependent variables. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference between usage of banking schemes of inclusive finance on socio economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil nadu.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that banking schemes and financial inclusion initiatives play a crucial role in enhancing the socio-economic development of rural and tribal women in Tamil Nadu. The findings clearly demonstrate that access, availability, and usage of banking services significantly influence improvements in both social and economic conditions. Regression analysis indicates a strong relationship between inclusive finance variables and development indicators such as growth, stability, employability, standard of living, and social upliftment, with all variables showing statistical significance. The research highlights that improved access to banking services empowers women by increasing their financial independence, decision-making ability, and participation in economic activities. Availability of services such as loans, savings schemes, and insurance further supports income generation and reduces dependence on informal credit sources. Moreover, the usage of banking facilities such as regular savings, credit utilization, and participation in financial schemes has the strongest impact on socio-economic advancement. However, the study also reveals persistent challenges, including low financial literacy, inadequate infrastructure, and socio-cultural barriers, which limit the full benefits of financial inclusion. Education emerges as a key determinant, as women with higher educational levels are more likely to utilize banking

services effectively. Overall, the study emphasizes the need for targeted policy interventions, including financial literacy programs, improved banking outreach, and digital financial services. Strengthening these areas will ensure more inclusive participation and sustainable empowerment of rural and tribal women, ultimately contributing to broader economic development and social equity.

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